

PIANO WORK BY LUDWIG VAN BEETHOVEN

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Annotation: this article provides detailed scientific information about the piano work of the composer Ludwig Van Beethoven, one of the founders of the Vienna classical school and who left a name in World Classical Music Culture with his indelible oeuvre.

Keywords: Music, Piano instrument, Vienna classical school, sonata, Concerto, Appassionata, Moon Sonata.

Beethoven was a great piano player of his time. By the end of the 18th century the master of Italian instruments was B. The piano made by Christopher gradually began to squeeze the harpsichord. Having mastered the technique of performing on the piano, Beethoven impressed all listeners with his excellent performance skills. The piano, which has loud, bright and melodic sounds, was his favorite sauce. For this sound, the composer wrote works throughout his creative path. Sonatas, variations, over 60 different pesas are examples. Among these, 32 sonatas are popular works. The piano sonata was a convenient form of expression of thoughts and feelings that excited composer Beethoven. In the 32 sonata orsts created by the composer, three are extremely popular. These are the "pathetic" sonata No. 8, the "Moon" Sonata No. 14, and the "Appassionata" No. 23.

"Pathetic" sonata.

The Sonata, which comes under number eight, was written by the composer in 1798, calling it a "great pathetic" sonata. The word "pathetics" comes from the Greek word "Paphos", and gives the mano" a work in a high mood". This "Rising Spirit" is characteristic of the music of all three parts of the Sonata, but the "Rising Spirit" is expressed in different ways in each part. The Sonata is scored in the tonality of do minor.

The music of the first movement is in sonata allegro form. But the development of music differs from the development in Gaydn's and Mozart's sonatas in its distinctive features. The Sonata begins with a slow-paced introduction theme. In the style of a tragic and at the same time solemn question, chords sound. The melody in a gloomy, lyrical mood is given in response. The main theme, played at a very fast pace after the introductory section, is reminiscent of waves that rise and fall violently. The auxiliary theme is very beautiful, in a melodic character. Mordent decorations give a special beauty to the tune final mazu in the usual closing character. The development section reworked the lyrical character section of the main theme and introductory theme. In the Repriza section, the exposition was repeated with a slight modification. Before the conclusion of the first part, the main theme is repeated with great force at a very rapid pace, and this thing expresses a high mood and indicates that aspiration, determination prevail.

The second part of the Sonata is performed in a very slow and melodic manner. The music describes the mental state of a person who is deeply contemplated on very important

and serious issues. In the first movement, the uplifting mood is expressed through bright music, while in this part it is reflected in the depiction of the human mind and intelligence.

The third part of the Sonata is written in rondo form. The music is played at a fast pace, being an exciting character. But this music lacks the intensity inherent in the music of the first part. The difference between the melodies is also not so great. The third movement is written in rondo form. The main theme is repeated four times. It is a musical theme of an exciting lyrical nature that determines the character of the music of the whole part. Beethoven's "pathetic Sonata" is an extremely popular work, in stark contrast to the sonatas created by composers Haydn and Mozart. Beethoven's work paved the way for further development of the sonata genre.

"Sonata of the month"

Beethoven's Sonata, written under number 14, is known as the "sonata of the Moon". The composer's contemporary poet L. Relshtab called the work by that name. In his opinion, the music of the first part of the Sonata describes a clear night landscape and a human mood given to lyrical fantasies. The Sonata is written in *do* minor tonality and consists of three movements. Beethoven called the work a "fantasy-style sonata". Indeed the first part of the Sonata is written in free form, not in the usual sonata *allegro* form. So the composer innovated in the sonata genre with this work as well. The composition of this Sonata was caused by a tragic event in the life of the composer - unlucky love, and this theme is shown in the music.

The first part of the Sonata - *Adagio*-depicts the deep sadness and tragic thoughts of an unhappy person whose love is left unanswered. Music is in many ways reminiscent of BAX's choral preludes.

The second part of the Sonata, *The Music of Allegretto*, is very beautiful and feminine. The music depicts the image of a very beautiful but light-hearted girl. This part is not much in shape, it is a vivid episode between the first part of a tragic, sad character and the violent third part.

The third movement, the finale, is in sonata *allegro* form. The music, played at a very fast pace, can be described as a "burnt, spiritually oppressed lullaby". At a very rapid pace, musical themes of a terrible and sad character pass. In doing so, the composer described the mental state of a person who was hit by the terrible blows of fate.

Beethoven's "sonata of the Moon" is considered one of the composer's best-known works and is among the most outstanding works of World piano music. The fame of the "sonata of the moon" lies not only in the beauty of the music and the depth of the emotions, but in the integrity of the work. All three parts of the Sonata are perceived by the listener as inseparable, holistic. The entire sonata music describes how exciting emotions grow and develop into an incredibly strong heartbeat.

Sonata No. 23 "Appassionata"

Beethoven's Sonata, written under number 23, is considered one of the greatest, masterpiece works of all world music literature. According to the great French writer Romain Rollan, this sonata is among the composer's other Sonatas, "like Monblanc, a basket is pouring over the other peaks of the Alps". Beethoven did not name the Sonata as "Appassionata", but it is worth saying that the title expresses the essence of the music very correctly. "Appassionata" means "full of pleasure, passionate".

The work describes a very strong aspiration, struggle, revolt of the heart and the coming of passions to junbush. When Beethoven was asked about the contents of this Sonata, it turned out that he briefly put "Read Shakespeare's "storm". But the composer did not want to say that in doing so, "I described Shakespeare's work in music." Beethoven's other Sonatas may be challenged by the "Appassionata" regarding the beauty of their musical themes. But in terms of the intensity of the dynamics, one of their Hecht cannot reach the "Appassionata".

The Sonata is written in the tonality of fa minor and consists of three movements. Although the music of the parts is of a different character, the integrity characteristic of the Sonata is characteristic. The first movement is in sonata allegro form. The main theme in the exposition is in a tragic character. The auxiliary theme is different from the main theme, being in a bright, calm character. Through the development of these two themes, the composer skillfully described the scenes of the struggle without frost in the first movement. The second part of the Sonata is written in the form of Andante variacias. Music, calm, in a lyrical mood. This part is a vivid episode between the first and third episodes, where passions come to junbush and fierce struggles are depicted..

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